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²³ CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of interconnected computing devices, machines, and digital devices, as well as objects, animals, and people. All of these devices have unique identifiers and ¹⁹ the capability to transmit data over the internet without the need for human-to-human or human-to-human interaction. It describes the idea of fusing commonplace physical objects with the Internet to enable communication between things and people.

A concept called ¹⁹ the Internet of Things (IoT) describes a linked and intelligently interconnected environment. A few examples of devices are sensors, Internet televisions, smartphones, electrical appliances, and other things. To gather and exchange data, they are equipped with electronics, software, sensors, and network connectivity [1].

² The electronic, electrical, and various mechanical systems utilized in many kinds of infrastructures are controlled and monitored by Internet of Things (IoT) devices. The devices that are linked ² to the cloud server are managed by a single user (also known as the admin), and any changes are then broadcast or informed to all authorized users connected to that network [2].

³³ The Internet of Things (IoT) envisions a world in which practically anything can be intelligently connected and communicated [3]. The proposed system focuses on the creation ⁴ of an Internet of Things-based online home automation system that enables users to automate and link all of their devices and home appliances to ensure seamless control over every area of their residence. The system is built to transmit data and enable remote control of household appliances. The cloud is used to transmit data from sensors via the Wi-Fi module, and after that, it applies a machine learning algorithm that also assesses the effectiveness of electronic

devices. It also helps to achieve power control and local data exchange that provide the user interface, stores all information about a particular house, and receives requests for information about the features of a single home appliance [1].

A technology known as home automation offers users in their homes and surrounding areas comfort, convenience, security, and energy efficiency. Both old people and people who are disabled and need assistance or institutional care have a higher quality of life when intelligence is present in their neighborhood. Recently, there has been a significant increase in home automation due to its affordability and the development of tablets and smartphones, which enable vast interconnection.

1.2 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

11 This project aims to design and implement an IoT Based Smart Home Automation system over the cloud.

The following objectives have been set forward to help attain this Aim:

- i. To Design a wireless Electrical load control system
- ii. To implement the design using the NodeMCU Esp8266 module
- iii. To interface the web App/Google assistance with the system
- iv. To evaluate the performance of the developed system

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

To alleviate our society's energy consumption problem, as well as to assist the elderly and disabled. Because they can utilize the internet to turn things on and off without having to move. As well as to ensure the consumers' safety and security at home.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PROJECT

Utilizing home automation could lead to more efficient and intelligent energy-saving techniques. By integrating the internet with a power system, the user at home can decide whether to switch on/off the appliance, leading to overall environmental impacts and lower electricity bills for the consumers using the system. To anticipate consumer needs and balance that with energy consumption. This research project helps improve safety and security at home; this allows users to monitor their homes while away. The findings of this study will directly benefit and assist the aged and those with disabilities.

1.5 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The project entails developing a WIFI-based wireless electrical load control system that includes a microcontroller-based unit, a Web-based application, and Google assistance. The control of three appliances will be the focus of this study: a lamp, a fan, and a door. The devices will be operated using a Web-based application along with Google assistance.

1.6 ORGANIZATION OF PROJECT

The development of a wireless electrical load control system is the focus of this research. The report is divided into five distinct chapters. The second chapter is a summary of the many kinds of literature that have been surveyed, including theoretical and historical context. The method and material required to execute this project are discussed in Chapter three, methodology section. This project's tests and results are presented in Chapter four, which details the tests carried out and the results obtained using the technique used in this project. The conclusion and recommendations are provided in Chapter five.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter entails the historical background, theoretical review, and review of related work as they are the best suited for the design of this project.

2.2 HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

Labor-saving devices were the foundation of early home automation. Self-contained electric or gas-powered home appliances first appeared in the 1900s as a result of the development of electric power distribution. These appliances included refrigerators, sewing machines, dishwashers, clothes dryers, washing machines (1904), water heaters (1889), and refrigerators [4].

One could argue that the adoption of the X10 technology standard marked the start of modern home automation technologies. The X10 standard was created by Pico Electronics in 1975 and later co-developed by Birmingham Sound Reproducers, established the foundation for granting remote control access to home appliances. Through the use of radio frequency bursts, the X10 standard was created to enable transmitters and receivers to operate over existing electrical wiring systems [5].

2.3 THEORETICAL REVIEW

A home automation system reduces energy consumption and improves the convenience of using different household equipment. Home automation or building automation today makes living very easy thanks to the energy-saving approach. It entails the wireless communication-based automatic control of all electrical and electronic equipment in homes. With the help of

this system, it is possible to centrally control lighting, heating, cooling, audio/video, security, kitchen appliances, and all other home-related equipment.

2.3.1 Forms of Home Automation Systems

There are mainly three forms of home automation systems:

1. Home Automation based on Power line
2. Bus Cable Home Automation or wired Based Home Automation
3. Home Automation operating wirelessly

1. Home Automation Based on Power line: Powerline communication is a progressing technology that utilizes electric power lines for efficient, the instantaneous transmission of data[6]. Powerline systems, which can be either AC or DC systems, employ regular electrical power lines to carry data [7]. A unique form of communication called power line communications might be able to close the current gap between the electrical and communication networks. An office or residential unit can have a variety of devices accessible at any time thanks to the use of a vast network of power lines and the connecting of several gadgets to this network that could communicate via this complex system [6].

It is a far less expensive technology that leverages already existing power lines for data transmission instead of additional cables, which would require additional installation costs. Because of the high level of complexity involved in this design, additional converter circuits and devices are required.

2. Bus Cable Home Automation or wired Based Home Automation

To send information, the wired home automation system uses Cat 5 cables. A control center is connected to the system. This system can be used in both new and old homes, like other

types of home automation systems; however it works best in newer homes. This is a fantastic choice for home automation. This is a dependable system that is simple to connect to additional gadgets. The home appliances are connected to a programmable logic controller, which is used in this home automation system. Actuators assist the machinery in receiving instructions from the primary controller [8].

All of the home's appliances are connected via a communication line to a main controller, or programmable logic controller. To communicate with the central controller, the appliances are connected to actuators. Computers that are in constant contact with the central controller concentrate the entire operation.

3. Home Automation operating wirelessly: These days, wireless technology is prevalent everywhere. You can link numerous systems wirelessly instead of running cables within walls. You may rely on Wi-Fi to link your home's electronic equipment. Because of their durability and ease of installation, wireless home automation systems have been the preferred choice[8]. This is the best option for any user of home automation.

However, you must confirm that the technologies you're utilizing are compatible with open networks. The system needs to be thoroughly examined before installation. Technologies including Bluetooth, GSM, WIFI, IR, and others are used by wireless home automation systems. More benefits than the other two types of home automation systems are provided by this one.

2.4 REVIEW OF RELATED WORK

In the literature, various home automation systems with various features and requirements were offered. [9] suggested home automation using Bluetooth and an Arduino to manage the appliances. This system uses a variety of cutting-edge technology sensors to manage modest household appliances. Using Bluetooth, users may manage and monitor the status of their

home equipment. This system's drawback is that it is unable to operate appliances at faraway locations.

In [10] also a ²⁷ Bluetooth-based home automation system is suggested. The study explains how Bluetooth technology is used for home automation networking and electrical appliance monitoring. Mobile phones, ARM9 processors, Arduino boards, remote controls, and various home appliances make up the envisioned network. The method is also cost-effective; however it has the drawback of an access latency caused by sharing ²⁷ a single Bluetooth module between numerous devices. In [11] ¹² proposed a ZigBee-based home automation system and Wi-Fi network are integrated through a common home gateway. The home gateway provides network interoperability, a user interface that is straightforward and adaptable, remote system access, Through a range ²⁵ of controls, including a remote control based on ZigBee and any Wi-Fi-enabled device that supports Java, the system enables homeowners to keep track of and regulate connected gadgets in home. The architecture is made to simplify the system and cut back on spending. is only compatible with Internet-enabled devices that run Java, and it uses a lot of power.

[12] Propose a home security system using a PC and Microcontroller. After researching the method used to control a home automation system utilizing power line communication technology, which is covered in a previous paper, the concept for this project was formed. In order to accomplish this, the user must operate the desktop at the precise moment he wants the appliance shut off. The advantage of this design is security; you cannot access the appliance control because the code is predefined in the program for the control of the appliances. Its limitation is, is a wired system, and only seven ports can be accessed at one time.

¹ The paper proposed by [13] demonstrates how intelligent home automation is run and managed. In this paper, the smart GSM-based home automation system includes a smartphone, PIC Microcontroller, and GSM modem. ¹⁰ The proposed research work is focused on the functionality of the GSM protocol, which allows the user to control the target system away from residential using the frequency bandwidths; ²⁰ incoming SMS message is sent from the user's phone to the GSM modem as a text message via the cellular network. The PIC microcontroller receives the orders from the GSM modem via an RS232 interface in text mode. From their mobile phones, ¹⁰ homeowners will be able to get feedback on the state of any household equipment they are in control of, whether they are turned on or off. Although it has excellent coverage and security, the system and SMS prices rely on the network.

²² In [14] a Smart Home Automation: GSM Security System Design & Implementation was proposed. A mobile application that runs on a Smartphone, tablet, laptop, and PC with Wi-Fi module servers is used by the author's system. This technology offers a method for web server-based home appliance control. Property can be managed by an owner through SMS texts made from a pre-registered cell device while at work. This system ignores an SMS sent from an illegitimate mobile number.

In the event of an invasion, the proposed systems electronic control device and security devices inform the proprietor via Text. The system is efficient, simple to operate, and offers security but its limitation is high costs in implementation, network dependent, and SMS costs.

⁶ In [15] designed a Dual Tone Multi-Frequency (DTMF) based home automation system using a microcontroller with a portable power supply. ³ The user calls a SIM number assigned to the home and presses the digits on their phone's keypad to control the home's devices by generating a DTMF tone. The tone is received and decoded by the GSM module at home using a DTMF decoder. The decoded instructions are passed to the microcontroller so that

user commands can be implemented at home. The system is portable since it is accompanied by a variable power supply. its drawbacks are Security issues may arise since any unauthorized person can access the devices at home. The absence of feedback will result in uncertainty of whether the task is performed or not on pressing the corresponding key.

In [16] designed an IoT-based Monitoring and Control System for Home Automation using Raspberry pi. The project proposes an efficient implementation of IoT (Internet of Things) used for monitoring and controlling home appliances via World Wide Web. Using Wi-Fi as a communication channel and the Raspberry Pi as a server platform, this project intends to operate household appliances through Smartphone. Whereas home appliances like lights, fans, and door locks are remotely managed through an intuitive website, the user will interact directly with the system in this case through a web-based interface. The server will be connected to relay hardware circuits that manage the home appliances. The user is able to choose the right device thanks to connection with the server. The user can select an appropriate device thanks to communication with the server.

[17]propose a Smart Home Automation and Security System using Arduino and IoT. In this paper, they present a security and automation for the home. Using Arduino, the sensors will be connected. Using the wireless module, the wireless module will transfer the status of our home appliances to a cloud platform. The same wireless network should be used to link both our system and Smartphone. In order to control which sensors the user can enable or disable, sensors were used. To operate the appliances, the flex sensors will be dependent on finger motions. In terms of sensing, monitoring, and control systems, this architecture offers a reasonable and less expensive solution.

To reduce the setback in the aforementioned systems, the system developed utilized several features and processes to achieve an ideal smart home. Most of the systems do not offer an

easy-to-use interface for controlling the dwellings. Another option for safe and real-time monitoring even while the user is away from home is to use the right cloud [18]. So; there is a need for an efficient home automation system that deals with the above-raised concerns in the current high-tech era. Here, we are proposing an IoT-based home automation system using NodeMCU ESP8266 that addresses the upraised issues.

The proposed solution is not just cost-effective but also, it's easy and reliable when it comes in the terms of implementation and programming. This system will provide real-time feedback as the user will be able to check what is happening at home. Utilizing IoT-based devices, the suggested system is inexpensive and effective at monitoring. The ESP8266 NodeMCU microcontroller utilizes a variety of modules.

CHAPTER THREE

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter highlights the methodology adopted for the design. It entails the system description of hardware and software design; it shows the analysis of the design components and specifications of the circuit. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, which is connected to electronic equipment, is used in the suggested system. It links to the cloud using a Wi-Fi network. Opening the door will allow the user to control the fan and light. A main controller unit (Main Switching of the House Circuit) connected to the always-on Wi-Fi network can be used to construct the smart home. Additionally, the sub-units are connected to the main controller so that non-smart appliances can be transformed into smart ones.

In order to preserve the communication link, consumers can access and control their smart home using Google Assistant and web-based services.

The various components selected for the design in chapter three were gotten ensuring that each of these components conform to the specifications. The design is divided into two:

- I. Hardware Design
- II. Software Design

Each section of the design comprises a component that performs different functions that are for the overall operation of the entire system.

3.2 HARDWARE DESIGN

This hardware implementation contains 3 different parts. (i) A 16X2 LCD for displaying the status of the system and IP address of the local Wi-Fi network (ii) Relay for switching the

load automatically and (iii) esp8266 for connecting to local Wi-Fi. The diagram in figure 3.1 shows the diagram of the system.

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Figure 3.1 Block Diagram of the system

Figure 3.2 depicts the circuit diagram for the system, which includes each component used to implement the suggested system.

Figure 3.2 Circuit Diagram of the System

Hardware Components Required:

1. NodeMCU ESP 8266 Wi-Fi controller board
2. 16x2 LCD Display
3. 2-channel 5v DC Relay Module
4. Servo Motor
5. Power supply

3.2.1 NodeMCU ESP 8266 Wi-Fi controller board

The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi microprocessor created in Shanghai, China by Espressif Systems, fitted with a microcontroller and a comprehensive TCP/IP stack. The Microcontroller board with 1 MiB of internal storage is called the ESP8285. that makes it possible to create single-chip gadgets that can communicate with Wi-Fi [1]. NodeMCU's 32-bit Tensilica Xtensa LX106 CPU runs at 8 MHz It is a standalone Wi-Fi networking solution that can execute standalone programs and serves as a bridge between the current generation of microcontrollers and Wi-Fi. NodeMCU features built-in TCP/IP, 10 GPIOs, 20 kb of RAM, and 4 MB of onboard storage, making it simple to connect to devices like sensors and actuators.

To upload the software, a USB cable is used to connect the built-in USB port to the laptop, just like other development boards available for purchase, such as Arduino and Raspberry Pi. NodeMCU has numerous advantages over Arduino UNO, such as being more affordable, simpler to use, intelligent, having a power regulator integrated, as well as a more potent processor. The pin diagram is shown in figure 3.4, and figure 3.3 depicts the NodeMCU ESP 8266.

Figure 3.3 NodeMCU ESP8266

Figure 3.4 ESP 8266 Pin Diagram

Table 3.1: ESP8266 Module Specification

Parameter	Specification
Input voltage supply	+3.3v
Input Current	100mA
Memory Capacity	512KB
Source Current	12mA
Communication type	Serial
Bandwidth	11-72 mbit/S
Power Consumption	100mW
Range	150m
Frequency	5.8ghz
Cost Factor	Low cost

3.2.2 16x2 LCD Display

The 16x2 LCD Display is depicted in Figure 3.5. The created system uses a generic LCD as its display device (liquid crystal display) 32 characters may be displayed on the screen in 16 columns and 2 rows. The LCD is interfaced to the controller in serial mode using 4 (four) data pins (d4, d5, d6, and d7) to exchange communication, while the Vcc and Vdd were connected to the positive +5v supply and ground respectively. A potentiometer (10k Ohm) is connected to the positive +5v supply and ground respectively. A potentiometer (10k Ohm) is connected to the Vcc pin of the display to control brightness. The LCD utilized for the system's display is depicted in Figure 3.7. The RS and EN pins are connected to the digital

pins of the controller to cause the LCD to write the characters on the screen while the RW pin is grounded and the serial pins D4, D5, D6, and D7 are configured serially when the display is powered.

Figure 3.5 16x2 LCD Display

3.2.32-Channel 5v DC Relay Module

³ A relay is an electromagnetic switch. When a very small microampere is connected to it, it activates. Typically, a relay is used in a circuit as a type of programmed switch. When a circuit is being built, the voltage that will activate it must be taken into account[17]. The apparatuses are switched ON/OFF in this system using the relay circuit. The NodeMCU microcontroller is responsible for providing the high/low sign. By default, when the "ON" command is sent, the output terminal of the relay connected to the load is open. from the remote terminalBy setting the relay's input terminal to "HIGH," the controller causes the matching output terminal to change from its default state of being open to closed, energizing the terminal. Upon receiving the "OFF" command, the terminal load is de-energized and the relay is set to LOW. A 2-channel 5v DC Relay Module is depicted in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6 2-Channel 5v DC Relay Module

3.3.4 Servo Motor

In Figure 3.7, a servo motor is shown. A motor, which is a rotary or linear actuator, can precisely control angular or linear position, velocity, and acceleration. This gadget consists of a suitable motor and a position feedback sensor. A closed-loop control system is made up of a servo motor, a shaft, a resolver or an encoder, a potentiometer, a driving gear, and an amplifier. A self-contained electrical device known as a servo motor precisely and effectively rotates a machine component.

[18] A servo motor in this configuration automatically controls the door. It enables both automated opening and closing of the door as well as manual control via a mobile application.

Figure 3.7 Servo Motor

3.3 SOFTWARE DESIGN

For programming and controlling, we've used three different software packages. The open-source IDE program is used to upload code to the NodeMCU ESP8266 in addition to

developing programs. The play store for Android smartphones hosts an Android application for ESP8266 that offers a platform for controlling various loads. Only ² if it is connected to the IP address and port supplied by the ESP8266 module will this function. Users can alter the application's settings, including the load name, the number of loads, the ON time, etc. provides real-time notification and ESP8266 control using a PC or web browser.

Software requirements

- I. Arduino IDE
- II. Google Assistant
- III. Android app

3.3.1 ARDUINO IDE

The Arduino IDE is a tool for writing scripts and uploading them to NodeMCU boards. Both the system's modules and the IoT automated home system are coded, debugged, and tested in this project using the Arduino IDE. A debugging component for usage with a number of Arduino boards, extra libraries, as well as a serial monitor for using the board in strange situations are included. are additional features of the Arduino IDE. Libraries for the Arduino platform are typically described as dot CPP files and are built using the wiring software abstraction.. Wiring enables easy procedures to quickly control hardware ports without consulting data sheets or delaying pin mapping. Because of this, the majority of the code for Arduino is written in C, even though it has some C and C++ components.

3.3.2 GOOGLE ASSISTANT

With the help of Google Assistant, you may ask or do things using voice commands. The abilities of Google Assistant vary depending on the device. You can access phone applications, set alarms, text people, check the weather, respond to questions, and operate lights and thermostats, among other things.

Google's voice-activated right hand is known as Google Assistant. While developing Google's present "OK Google" voice controls, it was first a precious extension of Google Now. In the beginning, Google Now shrewdly gathered important information for you: it knew where you worked, your gathering places and travel schedules, the entertainment packages you valued more, and what piqued your interest so it could provide you with specific information that had any kind of an impact.

In two-way conversations, Google Assistant can participate, following the organization's previous remote assistant. It is also available in a variety of languages, providing comfort to the customer.

FLOWCHART

Figure 3.8 shows the Flowchart of the program

Figure 3.8 Flow Chart

TEST, RESULT, AND DISCUSSION**4.1 INTRODUCTION**

The system was created and tested in modules, beginning with the circuit design and simulation on Proteus software. Next, the components were assembled on a breadboard to test their functionality before being moved and soldered onto the board's layout. Each component underwent a variety of tests to improve the operation and dependability of the circuits, including mechanical, frequency, and duration tests. Based on the methodology, the preliminary results for the designated Android software for the system control the connection on the breadboard as well as the circuit board and the entire system with the enc were also obtained.

The results and analyses for each section and subsection were also explained and shown on plates in order to have a proper circuit layout for simple troubleshooting, while the measurement and assessment of the test performed were also provided on tables in the appropriate manner.

4.1.1 COMPONENT TEST

The NodeMCU ESP8266 module, Relay module, and controller were used. Reference was made to the data sheets of the components used to confirm the power, frequency, and input/output specifications. Resistors were used as a protector to limit the current across the sensitive components, such as LCD, by using the color code to determine the value that is linked in series with the sensitive components. The connection to the breadboard is shown in Plate 4.1. When the system was turned on, each module was tested to make sure it matched the design specification and was also compatible with other connected components. These

tests were done as part of the initial arrangements made to determine how the system would operate.

Plate 4.1: Breadboard Connection of the developed system

The relay module and the servo motor are powered from the NodeMCU's 3.3v terminal, and the NodeMCU ESP 8266 module is connected directly to the DC adaptor (5V, 2.5A) when the system is powered on. Using a multimeter, the voltage distribution across the terminals of the components during system energization is displayed in table 4.1.

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Table 4.1 power supply testing at various points

Measured point	Meter reading in volts
Input Voltage supply	120V -230V
The terminal voltage of the DC adaptor	5V
The output voltage of the NodeMCU	3.3V
Servo Motor	3V
Terminal AC supply to the Load (Bulb and Fan)	Same as input supply

4.2 Software Test

The user will need ² to install the software on his or her laptop or Android phone after installing the experimental setup. The 16X2 LCD will display the IP address following successful software installation. After obtaining the IP address and port number, the user can log in to the Android application (plate 4.2). A home page that allows users to keep track of all the electrical and electronic equipment linked to the server will be visible as soon as the configuration is complete, as illustrated in plate 4.3.

Plate 4.2 Login interface of the android App

Plate 4.3 Dashboard of the Home Automation

In the proposed project, a mobile app is developed with all the capabilities necessary to control home appliances using speech recognition and device interoperability. All commands, including those for turning on and off the light, fan, and door, are available on the mobile app. Thus, this idea encompasses household smart appliances that can be electronically connected to mobile phones and operated over Wi-Fi. The choices to issue various commands to the appliances and operate them using our mobile app will be available in the mobile app on the phone. The login page for the app's main page will use the user's IP address and password to verify their identity. Once logged in successfully, the user can use speech recognition and a smartphone app to operate all of the appliances (Google Assistant).

The software will come with switches that may be modified manually or verbally by the user to manage the home's electronics and appliances.

Table 4.2 Software and connection mode

System Action	Response Time
Launch duration for the software	6s
Click on the response time	<8s
Average time for command delivery	Mobile App: 8s Google Assistant: 5s
Operating Frequency	5.8 GHz
Communication Range	140m-250m (outdoor)

4.3 Hardware Test

Table 4.3 displays the timing of events as recorded by the load monitoring unit. The hardware device must be powered on with an AC supply of 110-230V and initialized as well. The NodeMCU ESP8266 module at the load monitoring devices intercepts or receives the orders issued via the Android App and Google Assistant. On plate 4.4, the matching state of each terminal point that is presented on the LCD screen is depicted.

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Table 4.3 Timing of Events for the Receiver

Launching of the program script on processing IDE

Program start-up delay	<20s
NodeMCU initialization	30s

Figure 4.4: Terminal status display on LCD

4.4 Discussion of Results

The built system's individual components were tested one after another, and the android software and Google Assistant (a remote control unit) were created to work together with the load monitoring unit to create the entire system, producing the anticipated, trustworthy results. Android OS mobile devices run the software after installation. As soon as the hardware built at the load monitoring unit is powered on, the ESP8266 Wireless module starts a network and waits for a connection. Every time a command is given, the microcontroller processes it and uses the result to either turn on or off the load. The hardware and modeling of the smart home system were displayed as shown in plate 4.5. Three-terminal

load points—the Light, Fan, and Gate—are utilized as a prototype to assess the system's control, as shown on plate 4.7.

The system enables remote internet-connected control of the appliances from any location ²² in the world. The suggested home automation system is really put into practice, and as a result, results are attained.

Plate 4.5: Hardware and modeling of the system unit

Figure 4.6: Smart home automation system

Figure 4.7: Smart home automation system

11 CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

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In this paper, we have outlined a smart home automation controller unit's step-by-step process. The home appliance can be upgraded to a smart and intelligent gadget using IoT with the aid of the design control unit. To enable real-time control of home appliances, the designed Smart Home Automation system can be readily installed in a physical home. Using a Google Assistant voice command or an Android app, controlling home appliances is simple and effective. The study's results are favorable, and the suggested method can increase users' intellect, comfort, and safety. The recommended system has two advantages. First, we can simply monitor and access our smart home from anywhere utilizing IoT connectivity, which will prove to be energy-efficient.

Additionally, it provides assistance to the elderly and those with disabilities. The main motivation for this endeavor was the search for a solution to this issue. According to the purpose and goals of the work, the system was divided into units. The user-friendliness and portability of the Android hardware and software have been demonstrated.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the constraints identified throughout the investigation, this section offers suggestions for additional work, which include:

- I. More sensors and actuators can be added to the current system, such as a temperature sensor, to turn on or off the fan, a light, an air conditioner, etc. without using an Android app or Google Assistant.

II. The created system can also be enhanced to make it suitable for notifying the user of an incursion.

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